

Putative new plant viruses associated with *Plasmopara viticola*-infected grapevine samples

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6 2 **grapevine samples**
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44 18 **Abstract**

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46 19 In this study, we analysed a total of 16 libraries from over 150 grapevine leaf and grape samples
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48 20 infected with *Plasmopara viticola* (downy mildew of grapevine) to characterize the virome
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50 21 associated to this oomycete. Samples were collected in five distinct regions in Italy and in four
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52 22 different regions in Spain, representative of different pedoclimatic conditions and different
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54 23 grapevine cultivars during 2018 growing season. Due to the metagenomics nature of the samples
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56 24 (containing at least both downy mildew hyphae and spores, and grapevine cells residues), we were
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58 25 able to assemble several plant viruses and a few possible novel plant virus genomes with our *in-*
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3 26 *silico* analysis. We detected several plant virus variants already reported in grapevine, and a
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5 27 putative new ilarvirus previously unreported in grapevine. Furthermore, we characterized three new
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8 28 phenui-like viruses (in the order *Bunyavirales*), one of which shares some commonalities with plant
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10 29 coguviruses. Finally, we report a new strict association of three viral segments (one flavi-like and
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12 30 two virga-like) that we propose to be a new virus taxon named jivivirus.
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17 32 Keywords: jivivirus, coguvirus, ilarvirus, *Plasmopara viticola*, oomycetes
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21 34 **Introduction**

22 35 Grapevine is becoming more and more important worldwide, and its genetic variability and
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24 36 complexity is largely investigated since most of the cultivated varieties only represent a very limited
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27 37 layer of the current grapevine biodiversity (Anderson, 2014). A further layer of such biodiversity is
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29 38 contemplated when considering grapevine as a holobiont (an ecological unit made of strictly
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31 39 associated distinct species) to which corresponds a hologenome (the genomes associated in the
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33 40 ecological unit) (Moran and Sloan, 2015; Zilber-Rosenberg and Rosenberg, 2008; Rohwer *et al.*,
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35 41 2002). In our case, we are looking at grapevines loosely or strictly associated with a number of
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37 42 microorganisms, such as viruses, bacteria and fungi. This further layer of biodiversity has brought
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39 43 to a new concept on the aetiology of diseases caused by microorganisms: the pathobiome (Vayssier-
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41 44 Taussat *et al.*, 2014; Stecher *et al.*, 2012), representing the pathogenic agent that causes the disease
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43 45 and other microorganisms that interact with it.
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46 46 The holobiome/hologenome concept is not only important for giving the theoretical framework to
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48 47 the pathobiome systems but also because it underlines the importance of symbionts in providing
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50 48 phenotypic characteristics to an organism. In this respect, for example, viruses are often to be
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52 49 considered as part of their host “enhanced genome” because of the different features they might
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54 50 provide to their host. Up to a few years ago, most of the plant viruses were studied and
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56 51 characterized because of their pathogenicity. Nevertheless, in the early seventies, a number of
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3 52 viruses were defined “cryptic” because they were present in abundance in some wild and cultivated
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5 53 host plant species without causing obvious symptoms (Boccardo *et al.*, 1987). The role of these
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7 54 viruses in their plant or fungal host has been hypothesized in previous reviews (Roossinck and
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9 55 Bazan, 2017; Roossinck, 2015b). In fact, recent metagenomic approaches used for plant virus
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11 56 detection in natural environments have unveiled the abundance of symptomless viruses (Roossinck,
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13 57 2015a; Roossinck, 2015b), including some recently characterized mitochondrial plant viruses
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15 58 (Nerva *et al.*, 2019; Bruenn *et al.*, 2015). Published data suggest a possible positive role for
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17 59 symptomless viruses in providing resilience to abiotic stress to their hosts. Particularly relevant for
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19 60 grapevine is the role of grapevine rupestris stem pitting associated virus in resistance to drought
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21 61 (GRSPaV) (Perrone *et al.*, 2017).
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24 62 Nevertheless, viruses are potentially beneficial not only for their cryptic properties: some
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26 63 pathogenic (acute) viruses can have an interesting biotechnological potential if their hosts are pests
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28 64 or pathogens. Specific mycoviruses, for example, can be useful to contain the disease caused by the
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30 65 phytopathogenic fungus they infect (Dawe and Nuss, 2013; Turina and Rostagno, 2007; Xie and
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32 66 Jiang, 2014; Yu *et al.*, 2010); for this reason, in the framework of the H2020 funded project
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34 67 VIROPLANT, we collected isolates of *Plasmopara viticola*, the causal agent of grapevine downy
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36 68 mildew disease, from Italy and Spain and characterized the associated virome in order to use it as a
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38 69 biological/biotechnological platform to derive new approaches for the biocontrol of this disease. In
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40 70 this paper, we present the known plant viruses and possible new plant virus taxa that we have
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42 71 identified in the *P. viticola* metagenomics analysis.
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51 73 **Materials and methods**

52 74 **Grapevine sampling and total RNA extraction**

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54 75 In 2018, we collected a total of 158 grapevine leaf and grape samples with sporulating *P. viticola*
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56 76 and harvested mycelia and spores from the lesions with a brush submerging the lesions in Petri dish
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58 77 with sterile water (20 mL). The suspension was then centrifuged for 10 min at 5800 g in a Sorvall

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3 78 GSA rotor using adaptors for 15 mL Falcon tubes. The pellet was resuspended in 1 mL of water and
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5 79 transferred to 2 mL screw cap tubes. After a further spin at 14000 g for 1 min, the pellet was
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8 80 resuspended in Lysis buffer from the Spectrum Plant Total RNA kit (Sigma) and extracted with 0.5
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10 81 mL of 0.1 mm glass beads with a bead beater (FastPrep-24 MP Biomedicals). We sampled 43 sites
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12 82 across five regions in Italy (Veneto, Lombardy, Piedmont, Tuscany and Sicily) and 12 sites in four
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14 83 regions in Spain (Jerez, La Rioja, Penedés and Ribera de Duero). Only 141 RNA samples (74 from
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16 84 Italy and 67 from Spain) passed our quality standard for further analysis after UV
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18 85 spectrophotometry analysis. The RNA samples were then mixed in seven pools from Italy and nine
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20 86 pools from Spain of circa 6-10 samples/pool; each sample included in each pool had the same
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22 87 amount of RNA to avoid bias among different samples; the specific sampling location and
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24 88 contribution of the sample to each pool is displayed in Supplementary on line Table S1.
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30 90 **NGS and identification of putative plant viruses**

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33 91 Pooled RNA samples were sent for Ribosomal RNA depletion, Illumina TrueSeq library
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35 92 preparation and sequencing to Macrogen (Seoul, Republic of Korea) which provided over 100
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37 93 million reads (150 bases, pair ends) for each of the 16 libraries. The assembly and virus
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39 94 identification steps were performed as previously described (Nerva *et al.*, 2018). Reads from RNA-
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41 95 Seq were *de novo* assembled using Trinity version 2.3.2 (Haas *et al.*, 2013). Assembled contigs
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43 96 were then used as queries with Blastx against a custom viral database (<https://osf.io/c9x2p/>) to
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45 97 identify sequences of viral origin. The Blastx output was then manually screened for sequences of
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47 98 host origin which were removed from the subsequent analyses. Identified viral contigs were further
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49 99 assembled using the CAP3 sequence assembly program (Huang and Madan, 1999). The number of
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51 100 reads covering each viral genomic fragment was obtained by mapping the reads from each
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53 101 sequenced library on the assembled virus sequences with Burrows-Wheeler Aligner (BWA) and
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55 102 Samtools (Li and Durbin, 2009; Li *et al.*, 2009). ORF prediction, protein sequences and domain
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103 prediction were carried out with software freely available at NCBI (Li and Durbin, 2009; Li *et al.*,
104 2009). Reads mapping on the genomes were displayed using Tablet (Milne *et al.*, 2013).

106 **Estimation of the taxonomical complexity of the analyzed metagenomics sample**

107 A qualitative estimate of the taxonomical composition of each pooled sample was obtained through
108 MEGAN (Huson *et al.*, 2016). A quantitative assessment of reads aligning with *P.viticola* and *Vitis*
109 *vinifera* genomes (Yin *et al.*, 2017) was done with Bowtie (Langmead and Salzberg, 2012).

111 **Confirmation of virus presence by qRT-PCR**

112 Total RNA from individual samples was used as template to prepare random cDNA (High-Capacity
113 RNA-to-cDNA™ Kit, Applied Biosystems). For a number of putative plant viruses we traced their
114 presence to a specific RNA sample by quantitative reverse transcriptase PCR (qRT-PCR) following
115 protocols previously detailed (Picarelli *et al.*, 2019) and using the primer pairs displayed in
116 Supplementary on line Table S2.

118 **Phylogenetic analysis**

119 RNA-dependent-RNA-polymerase (RdRP) protein sequences from putative plant viruses were
120 aligned to closely related plant viruses using MUSCLE (Edgar, 2004) implemented in MEGA6
121 (Tamura *et al.*, 2013) in order to estimate their phylogenetic relationships with already
122 characterized viruses. The specific substitution model used in the Maximum Likelihood
123 methodology is detailed in each figure legend and was obtained with IQ-Tree with the inbuilt best
124 substitution model finder and the ultrafast bootstrap option (Lam-Tung *et al.*, 2015;
125 Kalyanamoorthy *et al.*, 2017; Diep Thi *et al.*, 2018). The accession numbers of the proteins used in
126 the alignments and the corresponding virus name and acronym are displayed in Supplementary on
127 line Table S3.

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Results and Discussion

P. viticola is an obligate biotrophic oomycete, and we could only characterize its virome in the context of a metagenomics sample (leaf or grape lesions with sporulating downy mildew) that included also some plant cell residues. Our virome analysis of the metagenomics samples mixed in 16 libraries (grapevine residues from leaves, grapes and downy mildew mycelia and spores) retrieved over 400 contigs carrying RdRP signature motifs (Wolf *et al.*, 2018), mostly belonging to mycoviruses that will be presented in a future publication. Here, we focused only on those putative viruses that are probably infecting the plant component of the sample, some of which could represent new taxonomic groups having as first hit in a Blastx search in the protein databases a confirmed plant virus (Table 1). The catalogue of viruses compiled for grapevine is already consistent (Martelli, 2017). Nevertheless, this catalogue is continuously growing through next generation sequencing approaches (also called high-throughput sequencing) of grapevine samples (Al Rwahnih *et al.*, 2009; Coetzee *et al.*, 2010; Al Rwahnih *et al.*, 2011; Zhang *et al.*, 2011; Giampetruzzi *et al.*, 2012; Poojari *et al.*, 2013; Fagundes Silva *et al.*, 2017; Jo *et al.*, 2017a; Jo *et al.*, 2017b; Jo *et al.*, 2017c; Beuve *et al.*, 2018; Diaz-Lara *et al.*, 2018; Hily *et al.*, 2018a; Zarghani *et al.*, 2018). This catalogue provides a rather complete framework to discuss the possible plant viruses we detected in our study.

Detection of plant viruses already reported in grapevine or in other plant species

Three libraries (corresponding to Italian samples) contain more than 500 reads mapping to a 13611 and a 3711 nt long contigs representing most of the grapevine leafroll associated virus 1 (GLRaV-1) genome, whereas six libraries including samples from both Spain and Italy contain more than 500 reads mapping to a full length genome (18304 nt) of grapevine leafroll associated virus 3 (GLRaV-3) (Table 1). Both closteroviruses are common throughout the grapevine growing regions. In this case, these infections were not associated to obvious leafroll symptoms, since we collected samples only from healthy looking grapevines (with *P. viticola* lesions).

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154 A contig of 7187 nt represents the almost full length RNA1 of the grapevine fanleaf virus (GFLV),
155 very abundantly present in four libraries from Spain with a percentage identity to the first hit in
156 Blast of 89% at the nt level. A second contig of 3770 nt putatively codes for the full length RNA2
157 of GFLV and is present in the same libraries as RNA1 (Table 1).

158 Eight libraries, representing samples from Italy and Spain, carried more than 500 reads mapping to
159 a contig representing the full-length sequence of grapevine pinot gris virus (GPNV), genus
160 *Trichovirus* in the *Betaflexyviridae* family that was recently found in both countries (Ruiz-Garcia
161 and Olmos, 2017; Bertazzon *et al.*, 2016) . The closest Blast hit is to a full length French isolate
162 (Beuve *et al.*, 2015), with 98% identity at the nt level.

163 We then assembled five contigs with matches to grapevine rupestris stem pitting virus (GRSPV).
164 The longest of these contigs represents the full-length genome and is present in 12 libraries both
165 from Italy and Spain; the other four contigs represent other partial genomes of the same species.
166 The five genomes represent all the four clades identified in a recent comprehensive work (Hily *et*
167 *al.*, 2018b) (not shown).

168 Finally, two complete sequences of genomes belonging to tomato mosaic virus (ToMV) and
169 tobacco mosaic virus (TMV) were assembled from our datasets. ToMV was present only in one
170 library representing Italian samples, whereas TMV was present rather abundantly in three libraries
171 from Spain (Table 1). Their genome is almost 100% identical to TMV and ToMV isolates present
172 in the NCBI databases (GenBank acc. numbers MK087763.1 and KR537870.1 respectively).

173 Given the biological and taxonomical complexity of the samples used for RNAseq it is not
174 surprising to find common grapevine viruses already reported in Spain and Italy, and therefore it is
175 safe to assume that these full length genomes are probably from the host plant. More puzzling is the
176 detection of two common tobamoviruses in two specific libraries, one in Italy and one in Spain.
177 Both viruses were previously reported in grapevine (Martelli, 2017), but TMV in particular was
178 shown to artificially infect *Phytophthora infestans* (Mascia *et al.*, 2019) and therefore we cannot

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3 179 exclude that the host is indeed *P. viticola*, given the close genetic relatedness of these oomycetes.
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5 180 Moreover, the natural presence and replication of a plant virus (cucumber mosaic virus) inside a
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8 181 fungus (*Rhizoctonia solani*) was demonstrated (Andika *et al.*, 2017), showing that cross-kingdom
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10 182 viral infection is possible in fungus coexisting with viruses infecting the same plants.
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13 183 **Detection of a putative new grapevine ilarvirus**

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15 184 All viruses so far described are not new for grapevine and represent already well-characterized plant
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18 185 virus taxonomic groups. Nevertheless, a possible new ilarvirus species is present in six libraries
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20 186 mostly representing Italian samples, including one Spanish library (DMS-10), with over 500 reads
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23 187 mapping each RNA segment (Table 1); for this virus we propose the name grapevine associated
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25 188 ilarvirus 1 (GaIV-1). The first ilarvirus segment is 3447 nt long and represents the almost full length
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27 189 segment encoding a protein carrying methyltransferase and helicase motifs. It has 81% identity at
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30 190 the amino acid level to tomato necrotic spot virus replicase (p1). The second segment is 2834 nt
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32 191 long and contains two ORFs, encoding the RdRP (protein 2a) and the protein 2b, a putative
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34 192 silencing suppressor. The closest virus present in the database is Parietaria mottle virus, with 71%
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36 193 identity at the amino acid level for the RdRP, whereas the closest 2b protein present in the database
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39 194 is that of tobacco streak virus with 66% identity at the amino acid level. The third segment
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41 195 putatively encodes both the movement protein (MP) and the coat protein (CP). The MP is 59%
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43 196 identical to the Parietaria mottle virus MP, whereas the CP is 56% identical to that of tobacco streak
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46 197 virus. Phylogenetic analysis of the RdRP encoding protein suggests the taxonomical placement of
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48 198 this virus as a new species in the genus *Iilarvirus* (Fig. 1). The three ilarvirus contigs are always
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50 199 associated in the same libraries, and when checking at the single sample level by specific qRT-PCR
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52 200 they also result strictly associated and present only in the sample DMG25 from Piedmont.
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55 201 In a recent review two grapevine-infecting ilarviruses were reported (Martelli, 2017): grapevine line
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57 202 pattern virus (GLPV) and grapevine angular mosaic virus (GAMoV) (Lehoczky *et al.*, 1987; Girgis
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60 203 *et al.*, 2009). A third ilarvirus was recently found in a metagenomic survey of grapevine in USA and

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was named grapevine virus S (Rott and Belton, unpublished, NCBI:txid1245593). The ilarvirus we found could only be compared to the two newest ilarviruses (the only two with available partial or complete sequences); therefore, in principle we can not exclude that our grapevine-associated ilarvirus sequence belongs to GLPV, although our isolate was detected on a virus symptomless vine, contrary to GLPV, which causes visible symptoms.

New grapevine viruses with coguvirus-like features

Surprisingly, we found three distinct contigs coding for proteins with RdRP domains closely related to phenuiviruses, a well characterized group of negative stranded insect viruses placed in the order *Bunyavirales*. One of these putative RdRPs is closely related to coguviruses, a recently characterized group of plant viruses (Xin *et al.*, 2017; Navarro *et al.*, 2018) also closely related to phenuiviruses and inside the *Bunyavirales*. The other two putative RdRPs have the highest similarity to a putative RdRP from laurel lake virus (LLV), a virus characterized from a metagenomic sample of adults *Ixodes scapularis* ticks (Tokarz *et al.*, 2018) (Table 1), also closely related to phenuiviruses. One RdRP encoded fragment is 6.7 kb in length whereas the other two are over 7.2 kb (Table 1). A phylogenetic tree that includes cogu- and phenui-like sequences shows that the two proteins encoded by the 7.2 kb fragment group together with the LLV and are separated from the 6.7 kb encoded RdRP (Fig. 2). We provisionally named the three viruses associated to each of these putative RdRP grapevine associated cogu-like virus 1 (GaCLV-1) (for the 6689 bases contig) and grapevine associated cogu-like virus 2 and 3 (GaCLV-2 and GaCLV-3), respectively, for the 7254 and 7251 bases long contigs.

In addition to the three RdRPs, we have detected in our dataset three distinct contigs coding for putative nucleocapsid proteins in coguvirus-like RdRP-positive libraries. One of them is most closely related to existing coguviruses and can be safely associated to GaCLV-1, since it is present in libraries and samples following a strict correlation in abundance and/or presence/absence (not shown). The other two putative nucleocapsids are associated to GaCLV-2 and GaCLV-3 and have a

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3 229 lower molecular mass (38.5 kDa for Nc of GaCLV1, and 28.2 kDa and 28.3 kDa for GaCLV2 and
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5 230 GaCLV3 Nc, respectively). The phylogenetic analysis suggests that these shorter Nc belong to a
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8 231 new putative genus of bunyaviruses separated from both plant coguviruses and insect phenuiviruses
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10 232 (Supplementary on line Fig S1). Surprisingly, Blastp searches reveal that a plant protein
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12 233 homologous to these nucleocapsids is present in some Arabidopsis genomes (Supplementary on line
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14 234 Fig. S1), which suggests that the potential to express the protein is still active; this could be a new
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17 235 example of endogenized viral sequence in the Arabidopsis genome after the well-known example of
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19 236 the partitivirus endogenized CP (ILR2) (Chiba *et al.*, 2011). As for the three contigs putatively
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21 237 encoding MP proteins, we predicted for one of them a very distinctive shorter MP (478 aa) that can
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24 238 be safely associated to grapevine associated cogu-like virus 1 and has a motif for an Aspartyl beta-
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26 239 hydroxylase N-terminal region (not shown). The MPs from the other two contigs were predicted to
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29 240 be much larger (689 aa for each protein) and are closely related to the LLV putative MP but have no
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31 241 conserved domains. Again, the phylogenetic analysis suggests that these MPs belong to a tentative
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33 242 new genus inside the order *Bunyavirales* (Supplementary on line Fig. S1), but in this case the MP
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35 243 from GaCLV-1 is also strongly associated to this clade. The MP-encoding segments associated to
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38 244 this tentative new genus encode an ORF also in the opposite orientation, however, such ORF has
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40 245 no match in the entire database, although some degree of conservation is shared among them
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43 246 (Supplementary on line Fig. S2).

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45 247 Our three viruses seem to be organized on a three-segmented genome base, since we failed
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47 248 numerous attempts to obtain a specific amplification product through nested RT-PCR spanning a
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49 249 putative intergenic region in an ambisense genomic segment that encodes both MP and Nc proteins.
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52 250 Therefore, each of these viruses has three segments: RNA1, RNA2 and RNA3 encoding the
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54 251 putative RdRP, MP and Nc, respectively (Table 1). This is contrary to what happens for proper
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56 252 coguviruses where the Nc and the putative MP are expressed from the same RNA segment in
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59 253 ambisense orientation. However, watermelon cogu-like viruses are still indicated as three-
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3 254 segmented genomes (Xin *et al.*, 2017). Other phenui-like plant viruses and LLV seem to be also

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5 255 organized on a three-segmented genome (Tokarz *et al.*, 2018; Wright *et al.*, 2018).

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8 256 In general, for the three phenui-like viruses here described, host placement based on existing

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10 257 phylogenetic relationships are puzzling, in particular since continuous addition of phenui-like

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12 258 viruses from different metagenomic samples (plants, insects and fungi) are carried out without

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14 259 direct evidence of the real host. Of the three phenui-like viruses here characterized, only GaCLV1 is

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16 260 closely related to bona fidea plant viruses (the citrus and watermelon coguviruses). Nevertheless,

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18 261 the tree topology of the putative MP somewhat challenges this placement, since also the putative

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20 262 GaCLV1 MP does not fall in the clades of the MPs belonging to plant-infecting viruses

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22 263 (Supplementary on line Fig. S2). Furthermore, two recent bona fidae mycoviruses have also been

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24 264 characterized, which are closely related to phenui-like coguviruses: Entoleuca phenui-like virus 1

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26 265 (Velasco *et al.*, 2019) and Lentinula edodes negative-strand RNA virus 2 (Lin *et al.*, 2019).

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28 266 Although none of the three phenui-like viruses we detected clearly associates in a clade with these

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30 267 mycoviruses, the close phylogenetic relatedness could suggest they are indeed mycoviruses. Based

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32 268 on the phylogenetic analyses, grapevine associated cogu-like virus 2 and 3 probably belong to a

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34 269 new family of bunya-like viruses distinct from the coguviruses, and we can not rule out the

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36 270 possibility that these are arthropods infecting viruses, since mites are often present and lay eggs in

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38 271 grapevine leaves and some arthropods sequences are present in our assembled contigs from the

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40 272 downy mildew grapevine lesions (not shown).

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44 274 **A previously undetected new association of virus segments to form a new putative virus**

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46 275 **taxon: the jviviruses**

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48 276 In a number of libraries we found the presence of a combination of three contigs of circa 4.1, 3.2

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50 277 and 2.2 kb in length (Table 1), that had the first Blastx hit to a combination of three segments: one

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52 278 of these segments has identity to flavi-like NS3 proteins (Jingmen tick virus and Citrus jingmen-

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3 279 like virus) and the other two share identities to helicase and methyltransferase domains (the 4 kb
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5 280 genome fragment) and RdRP domains (the 3 kb genome fragment) of virga-like viruses previously
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8 281 characterized from libraries of citrus leaf samples with citrus sudden death disease (Matsumura *et*
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10 282 *al.*, 2017). In the Italian and Spanish libraries we found two distinct combinations of these segments
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12 283 (Table 1). We verified that such association also extended to single samples in the pool
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15 284 corresponding to each Italian library. We observed that each of the three segments is present in each
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17 285 of the specific cDNA, and completely absent in other cDNA by checking with qRT-PCR using
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19 286 oligonucleotides specific for each segments (Table 3) with only one exception: sample DMG-110.
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21 287 This sample carries two such viruses but is missing one segment in one of the two viruses (raising
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24 288 the possibility of complementation or of the presence of a reassorted isolate). The three genomic
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26 289 segments of each of the two viruses, have fairly well conserved 5' and 3' ends (Fig. 3) supporting
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28 290 their association as a new tripartite virus. We suggest the name of grapevine associated jivivirus 1
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30 291 (GaJV-1) and grapevine associated jivivirus 2 (GaJV-2), respectively (from the first two letters of
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33 292 the words “Jingmen” and “virga”). Phylogenetic analysis confirms the previously observed
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35 293 association of these virus-encoded proteins to those of distantly related viruses, suggesting that if
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38 294 these genomic segments indeed are part of a single virus, they originated by reassortment of
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40 295 segments belonging to virga-like and flavi-like viruses (Fig. 4a, b and c).
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43 296 This association of virus segments is the second example of a multisegmented virus in which one of
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45 297 the viral segments derives from an unsegmented genome, as is the case of Jingmen tick virus
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47 298 (JMTV) formed by two distinct segments: two non-structural proteins (NS3-like and NS5-like) are
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50 299 encoded by two genomic segments likely derived from flaviviruses and the other two viral
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52 300 segments, with structural protein, are from unknown origin (Qin *et al.*, 2014). Origin of new virus
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54 301 taxa by reassortment was first shown for Ourmia melon virus (Rastgou *et al.*, 2009).
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A previously uncharacterized poty-like sequence

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304 Finally, we report here the identification of a contig of 7.8 kb which putatively encodes a
305 polyprotein very distantly related to plant potyviruses (the first hits in Blastx are beet mosaic virus
306 and zucchini yellow mosaic virus) (Table 1). A search for domains with CDD/sparkle (Marchler-
307 Bauer *et al.*, 2017) found an helicase, a C4 peptidase (typical of nuclear inclusion protein of
308 potyviruses) and a viral polymerase domain; when a typical plant potyvirus was analysed with the
309 same algorithm, a number of further conserved domain were found, among which are the peptidase
310 S3, the peptidase C6, potyvirid P3, poty PP and Poty Coat superfamilies. Such poty-like virus is
311 present in at least five of the Italian libraries but in none of the Spanish ones (Table 1). A
312 phylogenetic tree containing a few representatives of the *Potyviridae* family shows that this virus is
313 only distantly related to members of this family, occupying a very basal position in the branch that
314 associates it to the potyvirids (Fig. 5). We named this new virus Plasmopara associated poty-like
315 virus 1 (PaPLV 1) (Table 1). Only recently another potyviral-like sequence was assembled from a
316 plant sample and was proposed to be that of a new genus inside the potyviridae (Rose *et al.*, 2019),
317 but it has no significant homology with PaPLV1 which has a much shorter genome (7.9 kb versus
318 11.5 kb).

319 **Conflict of Interests**

320 The authors declare no conflict of interest for this work.

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For Peer Review

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3 332 **Figure legends**

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6 333 **Figure 1:** Phylogenetic analysis of a selected number of ilar-bromo like RNA dependent RNA
7 334 Polymerases (RdRP). The Maximum Likelihood (ML) methodology was used to infer the best tree.
8 335 After comparisons, the chosen best model of substitution was VT+F+I+G4. Consensus tree is
9 336 constructed from 1000 bootstrap trees. Log-likelihood of consensus tree: -27271.2615. The red
10 337 diamond indicates the viruses assembled in this work. At nodes the bootstrap values, expressed in
11 338 percentages.

12 339
13 340 **Figure 2:** Phylogenetic analysis of a selected number of phenui-like RNA dependent RNA
14 341 Polymerases (RdRP). The Maximum Likelihood (ML) methodology was used to infer the best tree.
15 342 Model of substitution: LG+F+I+G4. Consensus tree is constructed from 1000 bootstrap trees. Log-
16 343 likelihood of consensus tree: -61153.827700. Red diamonds indicate the viruses assembled in this
17 344 work. At nodes the percentage bootstrap values.

18 345
19 346 **Figure 3:** Nucleotide alignments of the 5'ends and of the 3'ends of the three putative genomic
20 347 segments (RNA1, RNA2, RNA3) belonging to grapevine associated jivivirus 1 and grapevine
21 348 associated jivivirus 2. Residues conserved in the three RNA are in yellow; those conserved in 2 out
22 349 of three are in blue. Alignments were performed using only the terminal parts of the genomic
23 350 RNAs, with ClustalX.

24 351
25 352 **Figure 4:** Phylogenetic analysis of a selected number of viral proteins closely related to those
26 353 expressed by jivivirus RNA1 (helicase, methyltransferase virga-like) (A), RNA2 (putative RdRP
27 354 virga-like) (B) and RNA3 (flavivirus NS3-like) (C). The Maximum Likelihood (ML) methodology
28 355 was used to infer the best tree. The best substitution models were WAG+F+I+G4 (for RNA1
29 356 expressed proteins) with a Log-likelihood of consensus tree: -24158.092193; Blosum62+F+I+G4
30 357 (for RNA2 expressed protein) with a Log-likelihood of the tree: -35144.3099; VT (for RNA3
31 358 expressed protein) with a Log-likelihood of the tree: -7608.1139. Red diamonds indicate the viruses
32 359 assembled in this work. At nodes the percentage bootstrap values.

33 360
34 361 **Figure 5:** Phylogenetic analysis of a selected number of Potyviridae-like RNA dependent RNA
35 362 Polymerases (RdRP). The Maximum Likelihood (ML) was used to infer the best tree. Model of
36 363 substitution: LG+F+I+G4. Consensus tree is constructed from 1000 bootstrap trees. Log-likelihood
37 364 of consensus tree is -371579.360049. A red diamond indicates the virus assembled in this work. At
38 365 the nodes the bootstrap values expressed in percentages.

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Table 2: Result of reverse transcription quantitative PCR (qRT-PCR) expressed as Ct max and min for each of the contigs of the three RNA segments corresponding to the grapevine associated cogu-like virus 1, 2 and 3 encoding for the three RdRPs. Only the positive samples are reported, but all the samples inside the pool have been tested, including negative controls. A negative control from another pool was also tested and included in the table.

Library	Specific sample	RNA1 segment	Ct max ^a	Ct min ^a	Location
DMG-A	DMG82	RdRp1	23.3	23.16	Piedmont
DMG-A	DMG82	RdRp2	26.2	26	Piedmont
DMG-B	DMG83	RdRp3	24.13	23.86	Piedmont
DMG-A	DMG86	RdRp2	23.93	23.85	Piedmont
DMG-A	DMG91	RdRp2	29.56	29.25	Piedmont
DMG-C	DMG12	RdRp1	N/A	N/A	Lombardy
DMG-C	DMG12	RdRp2	N/A	N/A	Lombardy
DMG-C	DMG12	RdRp3	N/A	N/A	Lombardy

^a N/A= no amplification

Table 3: Result of reverse transcription quantitative PCR (qRT-PCR) expressed as Ct min for each of the contigs of the six RNA segments corresponding to the grapevine associated jivivirus 1 (GaJV1) and grapevine associated jivivirus 2 (GaJV2)

Sample	Region	GaJV1- RNA3	GaJV1- RNA1	GaJV1- RNA2	GaJV2- RNA3	GaJV2- RNA1	GaJV2- RNA2
DMG109	Lombardy	24.81	24.08	24.49	0	0	0
DMG11	Lombardy	25.8	24.79	25.86	32.8	25.61	24.96
DMG110	Lombardy	24.36	23.31	0	28.87	29.56	28.13
DMG112	Lombardy	27.15	27.04	26.85	0	0	0
DMG116	Tuscany	25.76	23.49	24.49	0	0	0
DMG118	Piedmont	28.47	28.04	27.51	0	0	0
DMG119	Piedmont	29.34	28.64	29.03	0	0	0
DMG20	Piedmont	28.39	28.12	28.26	0	0	0
DMG33	Lombardy	28.01	24.24	24.57	0	0	0
DMG37	Lombardy	29.25	24.61	25.01	0	0	0
DMG39	Lombardy	26.55	26.26	26.73	0	0	0
DMG40	Lombardy	26.36	24.98	27.17	0	0	0
DMG41	Lombardy	28.55	25.79	26.38	0	0	0
DMG50	Veneto	28.84	26.37	27.42	0	0	0
DMG54	Lombardy	27.48	25.24	25.59	0	0	0
DMG56	Lombardy	29.71	25.71	25.7	0	0	0
DMG71	Tuscany	28.1	26.65	28.38	30.7	29.9	28.4
DMG85	Tuscany	29.06	27.29	28.47	0	0	0
DMG86	Piedmont	28.41	27.82	28.7	0	0	0
DMG90	Piedmont	28.45	27.68	27.53	0	0	0
DMG91	Piedmont	22.00	20.37	20.15	0	0	0
DMG94	Lombardy	27.45	26.13	26.49	0	0	0
DMG97	Lombardy	26.58	25.34	25.68	0	0	0

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Fig. 1:

Figure 1

190x275mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig. 2:

Figure 2

190x275mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig. 4

Figure 4

190x275mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Fig. 5:

Figure 5

190x275mm (300 x 300 DPI)